

Antioxidant effects of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on rats blood sample

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Abstract

The principle goal of the present article is to investigate the potential role of the ethanolic extracts of aerial parts of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* in management of oxidative stress in male rats treated with aluminum chloride (AlCl₃). Supplementation of drinking water with 0.3 g/L of aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) in a dose of 0.3 g/L for 16 weeks induced oxidative stress with significant increase in serum creatinine level, alanine transferase (ALT), aspartate transferase (AST) activity, malondialdehyde (MDA) and hepatic DNA fragmentation levels. However, oral administration of the ethanolic extract of *Jasonia candicans* or *Jasonia montana* at concentration of 150 mg/kg bw daily for 6 weeks showed significant decrease in serum creatinine and ALT activity associated with insignificant change in serum AST activity, MDA or DNA fragmentation level in liver tissues compared to the negative control group. The treatment with extracts in combination with AlCl₃ also resulted in significant decrease in the all studied parameters compared to the AlCl₃ treated one. In addition, the extracts could decrease significantly the frequency of chromosomal aberrations induced in bone marrow cells and spermatocytes of the rats treated with aluminum chloride (AlCl₃). High content of terpenes, sesquiterpenes and flavonoids in the ethanolic extracts of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* may be responsible for the antioxidative and antigenotoxic action. These results clearly suggested that the ethanolic extracts of aerial parts of *Jasonia candicans* or *Jasonia montana* may effectively ameliorate the oxidative stress resulted from AlCl₃ intoxication. Thus, these extracts may have therapeutic applications in the management of oxidative stress related diseases.

Keywords

Genotoxicity tests, Oxidative stress, *J. montana*, *J. candicans*, AlCl₃

Introduction

Aluminum (Al) is one of the most abundant metals in the earth's crust. Human exposure to Al has been increasing over the last decades. This element appears mainly in food products and in drinking water derived from both natural sources and treatment methods [1].

Oxidative stress induced damage was shown to be one of the important mechanisms to indicate that aluminum has an association with free radical production [2]. Aluminum is a non-redox-active metal which is capable of increasing the cellular oxidative milieu by potentiating the pro-oxidant properties of transition metals such as iron and copper [3]. An unusual aspect of the biochemistry of this non-redox-active metal is its pro-oxidant activity, which might be explained by the formation of an Al superoxide semi-reduced radical ion (AlO₂⁻²⁺) [4]. It can be speculated that aluminum induced oxidative damage to mitochondrial proteins may be one of the possible mechanisms for the onset of aluminum toxicity. It has been shown that chronic aluminum exposure is involved in the impairment of mitochondrial electron transport chain (ETC) and increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [5]. The formation of excessive ROS and

reactive nitrogen species (RNS) can lead to oxidative injury [6]

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) interact with all biological macromolecules, including lipids, proteins, nucleic acids, and carbohydrates. The resulting stress increases neuronal death, which contributes to the neuropathology associated with several diseases [7]. It has also been observed that acute ROS generation can inactivate the iron sulphur centers of ETC complexes I, II, III and aconitase resulting in decreased mitochondrial energy production [8]. Al induced depletion of glutathione (GSH) and reduction of activity of glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), glutathione S-transferase (GST) and catalase (CAT) [9].

The use of traditional medicine during last decade has expanded globally and is gaining popularity. The world health organization (WHO) reported in 2001 that the herbal medicine serve the health need of about 80% of the world's population, especially for millions of people in the vast rural areas of developing countries [10]

The genus *Jasonia*, of the family Asteraceae, tribe Linuleae, subtribe Linuleinae is a small genus with about five species and mainly distributed in the Mediterranean region [11]. Earlier work on the chemistry of four species, *J. glutinosa*, *J. mberosa*,

J. montana and *J. candicans*, revealed the presence of several sesquiterpenes and sesquiterpene lactone derivatives, eudesmanoic acid, eudesmanolides, [12] together with several polymethoxylated flavonoids and some coumarins [13]. Some species of this genus showed antibacterial activity [12] and some medicinal uses as an antispasmodic drug [14].

Plant sesquiterpenes are secondary metabolites widely distributed in the higher plant Kingdom and are known to show diverse biological and pharmacological actions, including anti-inflammatory activity [15]. Polyphenols exist in many plants and are especially abundant in *Jasonia montana* [16], are used as antioxidant. *J. montana* and polyphenol-enriched plant extracts have no known toxicity.

The current study was designed to investigate the potent role of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* ethanolic extract in the management of oxidative stress in experimental animal model.

Materials and Methods

Collection of plant material

The aerial parts of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* were collected from west of Alexandria and hilly areas from El-Arbaeen valley, Saint Catherine, South Sinai, Egypt, respectively in November 2009. The taxonomical features of the plants were kindly confirmed by Prof. M. N. El-Hadidi, Prof. of plant Taxonomy, Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt. Voucher specimens were kept in the museum of the Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.

Preparation of extracts

Two kgs of each of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* air dried plant materials were separately grounded and were exhaustively extracted by percolation in 70% aqueous ethanol at room temperature. The filtrates were concentrated under vacuum at 40°C to yield 170 g dried extract from *Jasonia candicans* and 200 g dried extract from *Jasonia montana*. Stock solutions were prepared by dissolving 60 g of each extract in 400 ml water [17].

Experimental design

Seventy seven adult male Sprague Dawley rats (200-250 g) were enrolled in the current study. The rats were obtained from the Animal House Colony of the National Research Centre, Dokki, Cairo, Egypt. The rats were housed in polypropylene cages in an environmentally controlled clean air room with a temperature of 24 ± 1°C, a 12 h light/ 12 h dark cycle, a relative humidity of 60 ± 5% and free access to tap water and food. Rats were allowed to adapt to these conditions for two weeks before beginning the experimental protocol. All animals received human care and use according to the guidelines for Animal Experiments which were approved by the Ethical Committee of Medical Research, National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt. Oxidative stress was induced in rats by supplementing the drinking water with aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) for 16 weeks [18]. The animals used in the current study were classified

into five groups: 1- Healthy control group (negative control), 2- *Jasonia candicans* treated group in which the animals were orally administered with *Jasonia candicans* extract in a dose of 150 mg/kg bw [19] daily for 6 weeks, 3- *Jasonia montana*- treated group in which the animals were orally administered with *Jasonia montana* extract in a dose of 150 mg/kg bw daily for 6 weeks, 4- AlCl₃ intoxicated group (positive control). AlCl₃ intoxicated group treated orally with *Jasonia candicans* extract (150 mg/kg bw) daily for 6 weeks, 5- Oxidative stress induced group treated orally with *Jasonia montana* extract (150 mg/kg bw) daily for 6 weeks.

At the end of the experimental period, the animals were fasted overnight and subjected to anesthesia using diethylether. The blood samples were collected from all animals in the different studied groups. Then, the animals were rapidly killed and the liver tissues were dissected for DNA fragmentation assay.

Biochemical analysis

Serum alanine transferase (ALT), aspartate transferase (AST) and creatinine activity was determined colourimetrically using kit purchased from Randox Co., Egypt, according to the method of Schmidt [20]. Serum creatinine level was determined using kit purchased from Randox Co., Egypt, according to the method described by [21].

DNA Fragmentation assay: The method of DNA fragmentation was carried out according to Perandones et al. [22]. About 0.25g of the liver tissues was mechanically dissociated in 400 µl hypotonic lysis buffer (10mM tris, 1mM EDTA and 0.2% triton X-100, pH 8.0). The cell lysate was centrifuged at 12,000 Xg for 15 min. the supernatant containing small DNA fragments was immediately separated as well as the pellet containing large pieces of DNA, were used for the diphenylamine (DPA) assay. The pellet was resuspended in 400 µl of hypotonic lysis buffer. 400µl 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added to both the supernatant and the resuspended pellet and incubated at room temperature for 10 min. The tubes were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 15 min. at 4°C. After discarding the supernatant, the precipitate was resuspended in 400 µl 5% TCA, incubated at 80°C for 30 min. and then allowed to cool at room temperature. After centrifugation, one volume of the extracted DNA was added to two volumes of colorimetric solution (0.088 M diphenylamine (DPA), 98% V/V glacial acetic acid, 1.5% V/V sulphuric acid and 0.5% V/V 1.6% Acetaldehyde solution). The samples were stored at 4°C for 48h. The colorimetric reaction was quantified spectrophotometrically at 578 nm. The percentage of DNA fragmentation was expressed by the formula:

$$\text{DNA fragmentation percentage} = \frac{\text{O.D supernatant}}{\text{O.D supernatant} + \text{O.D pellet}} \times 100$$

Lipid oxidation analysis by determination of malondialdehyde concentration: Lipid peroxidation was assayed by measuring the level of malondialdehyde (MDA). Malondialdehyde forms a 1:2 adduct with thiobarbituric acid which can be

measured by spectrophotometry. Malondialdehyde was determined by measuring thiobarbituric reactive species using the method of [23], in which the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances react with thiobarbituric acid to produce a red colored complex having peak absorbance at 532 nm.

Cytogenetic analysis

Rats were subjected to cytogenetic analysis from bone marrow cells using the method of Preston et al. [24]. Briefly, rats were injected intraperitoneally (i.p) with colchicine (0.05 mg/kg) for two and half hours before sacrifice. Animals were sacrificed and femoral bone marrow cells were flushed with isotonic solution (0.9%NaCl), hypotonic solution (0.56%KCl) was added to the cell pellet and incubated at 37 °C for 30 minutes, the solution was fixed, slides were prepared and stained using 10% Giemsa stain. Fifty metaphase spread for animal were analyzed for scoring the different types of chromosomal aberrations.

Statistical analysis

The results were expressed as Mean± S.D of the mean. Data were analyzed by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) program, version 11. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS-test) was used to determine if two datasets differ significantly followed by Bonferroni test as multiple comparison method to compare significance between groups [25]. Difference was considered significant when P value was <0.05.

Results

The data in Table (1) represented the effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on serum creatinine level, ALT activity and AST activity in AlCl₃ intoxicated group as an oxidative stress model. Administration of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts produced significant decrease (p>0.05) in serum creatinine level and ALT activity in comparison with the negative control group. While, administration of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts produced insignificant decrease in serum AST level in comparison with the negative control group. On the other hand, AlCl₃ intoxicated group showed significant increase (p>0.05) in serum creatinine level, ALT activity and AST activity in comparison with the negative control group. While the treatment of the aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) group with *Jasonia candicans* or *Jasonia montana* extracts produced significant decrease (p>0.05) in serum creatinine, ALT and AST in comparison with the AlCl₃ intoxicated group.

The data in Table (2) represented the effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on serum MDA and DNA fragmentation in liver tissues in oxidative stress model. Administration of *Jasonia candicans* extract produced significant decrease (p>0.05) in serum MDA in comparison with the negative control group, while administration of *Jasonia candicans* extract produced insignificant decrease in DNA fragmentation in liver tissues

in comparison with the negative control group. Administration of *Jasonia montana* extract produced insignificant decrease in serum MDA or DNA fragmentation in liver tissues in comparison with the negative control group. On the other hand, oxidative stress model (AlCl₃ treated group) showed significant increase (p>0.05) in serum MDA and DNA fragmentation in liver tissues in comparison with the negative control group. While treatment with *Jasonia candicans* or *Jasonia montana* extracts produced significant decrease (p>0.05) in serum MDA and DNA fragmentation in liver tissues of AlCl₃-treated rats in comparison with the untreated positive control group.

Group	Parameters		
	Creatinine [mg%]	AST [U/l]	ALT [U/l]
Negative control	0.517±0.004	44.66±0.362	38.16±0.35
<i>Jasonia candicans</i>	0.471±0.002*	43.83± 0.638	36 ± 0.267*
<i>Jasonia montana</i>	0.466±0.003*	43.83 ± 0.44	36.5 ± 0.31*
AlCl ₃ intoxicated group (positive control)	0.75± 0.010**	83 ± 0.534**	69.66±1.14**
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia candicans</i>	0.696±0.011*	73.34±0.883*	60.5± 0.313*
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia montana</i>	0.703±0.009*	74.166 ±0.811*	62.66 ± 0.556*

Table 1: Effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on creatinine level, ALT and AST activity in male rats received AlCl₃ in drinking water. Data are expressed as Mean ± SD. Values marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different (P < 0.05), (**) are significantly different (P < 0.01).

The data in Table (3) represented the effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on the frequency of structural and numerical chromosomal aberrations in bone marrow cells of the rats received AlCl₃ in drinking water. The results showed that structural chromosomal aberration in bone marrow cells of male rats especially gaps, breaks, fragments, endomitosis as well as total structural aberration and polyploidy increased significantly (high and very high significant) in the AlCl₃ treated group (group 4) compared with those in controls (positive and negative controls) treated with *Jasonia montana* or *Jasonia candicans* (group 1,2 and 3, respectively).

While, the treatment with *Jasonia Montana* and *Jasonia candicans* in combination with aluminum chloride (groups 5, 6), reduced the frequency of all types of structural and numerical chromosomal aberrations compared with aluminum chloride treated group but still differ significantly compared with those in controls.

Group	Parameters	MDA($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	DNA fragmentation (%)
Negative control		2.11 \pm 0.0349	12.16 \pm 0.349
<i>Jasonia candicans</i>		2.0 \pm 0.0267 [*]	11.33 \pm 0.244
<i>Jasonia Montana</i>		2.03 \pm 0.0244	11.5 \pm 0.163
AlCl ₃ intoxicated group (positive control)		3.85 \pm 0.025 ^{**}	29.66 \pm 0.244 ^{**}
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia candicans</i>		3.216 \pm 0.039 [*]	22.33 \pm 0.488 [*]
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia montana</i>		3.18 \pm 0.061 [*]	22.65 \pm 0.408 [*]

Table 2: *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on MDA and DNA fragmentation levels in male rats received AlCl₃ in drinking water. Data are expressed as Mean \pm SD. Values marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different (P < 0.05), (**) are significantly different (P < 0.01).

The results of germ cells (Table 4) showed increases of structural aberrations (chain, autosomal univalents, and x-y univalents) and total structural aberrations as well numerical variation (polyploidy) in aluminum chloride treated group (group 6) compared with control groups (groups 1, 2 and 3). However, the treatment with *J. montana* and *J. candicans* in combination with AlCl₃ reduced the frequency of all types of structural aberrations compared to those of control groups but the difference still significant.

Treatment	No. of animals	No. of examined cells	Structural Aberrations					Numerical aberrations	
			Gap	Break	Fragment	Endomitosis	Total aberrations	Polyploidy	
Negative Control	5	250	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	0.80 \pm 1.30 [*]	0.00 \pm 0.00	
<i>Jasonia candicans</i>	5	250	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	0.60 \pm 0.54 [*]	1.40 \pm 1.67 [*]	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	
<i>Jasonia montana</i>	5	250	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	0.80 \pm 1.09 [*]	0.20 \pm 0.44 [*]	
AlCl ₃ intoxicated group (positive control)	5	250	6.20 \pm 0.83 ^{***}	10.50 \pm 1.14 ^{***}	15.20 \pm 0.83 ^{***}	22.60 \pm 0.89 ^{***}	54.4 \pm 3.20 ^{***}	4.40 \pm 0.54 ^{***}	
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia candicans</i>	5	250	1.20 \pm 0.44 ^{**}	1.40 \pm 0.89 ^{**}	1.60 \pm 0.89 ^{**}	4.40 \pm 0.54 ^{**}	8.60 \pm 0.54 ^{**}	0.60 \pm 0.54 ^{**}	
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia montana</i>	5	250	1.60 \pm 0.54 ^{**}	1.40 \pm 0.54 ^{**}	1.60 \pm 0.89 ^{**}	9.40 \pm 1.14 ^{**}	14.00 \pm 1.00 ^{**}	1.20 \pm 0.44 ^{**}	

Table 3: Effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on the frequency of structural and numerical chromosomal aberrations in bone marrow cells of rats received AlCl₃ in drinking water. Data are expressed as Mean \pm SD. Values marked with an asterisk (*) are

significantly different (P < 0.05), (**) are significantly different (P < 0.01).

Treatment	No. of animals	No. of examined Cells	Structural aberrations			Total aberrations	Numerical aberrations
			Chain	Qutosomalunivalents	X-y univalents		
Negative Control	5	250	0.20 \pm 0.44	0.20 \pm 0.44	0.40 \pm 0.54	0.60 \pm 0.89	0.20 \pm 0.44
<i>Jasoniacandicans</i>	5	250	0.20 \pm 0.44	0.00 \pm 0.00	0.40 \pm 0.54	0.60 \pm 0.89	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]
<i>Jasoniamontana</i>	5	250	0.40 \pm 0.54 [*]	0.20 \pm 0.44	0.60 \pm 0.54 [*]	1.20 \pm 1.30 [*]	0.60 \pm 0.54 [*]
AlCl ₃ intoxicated group (positive control)	5	250	1.40 \pm 0.54 ^{***}	1.20 \pm 0.44 ^{***}	9.20 \pm 0.83 ^{***}	11.80 \pm 1.09 ^{***}	1.00 \pm 1.00 ^{***}
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia candicans</i>	5	250	0.80 \pm 0.50 [*]	0.80 \pm 0.83 [*]	5.00 \pm 0.70 ^{**}	6.60 \pm 1.51 ^{**}	1.20 \pm 1.30 [*]
AlCl ₃ + <i>Jasonia montana</i>	5	250	4.40 \pm 0.54 ^{***}	8.20 \pm 0.83 ^{***}	13.80 \pm 0.83 ^{***}	26.40 \pm 1.14 ^{***}	8.60 \pm 0.54 ^{***}

Table 4: Effect of *Jasonia candicans* and *Jasonia montana* extracts on the frequency of chromosome aberrations in spermatocytes of rats received AlCl₃ in drinking water. Data are expressed as Mean \pm SD. Values marked with an asterisk (*) are significantly different (P < 0.05), (**) are significantly different (P < 0.01) and (***) are significantly different (P < 0.01).

Discussion

The aim of the present study was to investigate the potent role of Jasoniacandicans and Jasonia Montana ethanolic extract in the management of oxidative stress in experimental animal model. The results revealed that supplementation of drinking water with AlCl₃ induced oxidative stress with significant increase in serum creatinine level, ALT, AST activity, MDA and DNA fragmentation levels. However, oral administration of the ethanolic extract of *J. candicans* or *J. montana* showed significant decrease in serum creatinine and ALT activity associated with insignificant change in serum AST activity, MDA or DNA fragmentation level compared to the negative control group. The treatment with extracts in combination with AlCl₃ also resulted in significant decrease in the all studied parameters compared to the AlCl₃ treated one. In addition, the extracts could decrease significantly the frequency of chromosomal aberrations induced in bone marrow cells and spermatocytes of the rats treated with aluminum chloride (AlCl₃).

Aluminum accumulates mainly in bones, spleen, liver and lungs [26]. Assessment of harmful effect of aluminum was based on the analysis of selected biochemical parameters. Statistically significant increase in serum creatinine concentration in animal receiving aluminum chloride is of interest. The increase of serum creatinine concentration can be a consequence of critical accumulation of this metal in kidneys and following renal failure development. Aluminum is excreted mainly by kidneys [27]. Chronic exposure to aluminum also results disruptions in mineral balance disturbances. In the biological systems aluminum ions replace iron and magnesium ions [28]. Also aluminum accumulates in liver and alter cellular membrane structures and increase the ALT and AST activity

[29]. Aluminum reduce Fe^{2+} binding to ferritin, and disturb heme synthesis [27]. Free iron ions released from biological complexes by aluminum can catalyze hydrogen peroxide decomposition to hydroxyl radical- according to Fenton's reaction. This high hydroxyl radical reactivity is able to initiate cellular damage, this cause the increase in hepatic DNA fragmentation level [30].

Aluminum has been reported to induce lipid peroxidation and to alter physiological and biochemical characteristics of the biological systems [31]. One possible explanation for the enhanced lipid peroxidation is that Al facilitates iron-induced lipid peroxidation [32], non-iron-induced lipid peroxidation [33] and non-iron-mediated formation of the hydroxyl radical [34]. Aluminum has the ability to bind to the membranes, since Al catalyses oxidative cascades for lipids much easier than it is for proteins. Aluminum also exhibits high affinity for phosphate groups and bind to the phospholipids head groups through electrostatic forces [35] which may disturb the order as well as other dynamic parameters of the bilayer. The consequential phospholipid rearrangement may aid in the propagation of lipid peroxidation and therefore increasing malondialdehyde concentration [31].

Aluminum is considered also as one of the contributing factors to oxidative stress, as it generates highly reactive oxy and hydroxyl free radicals directly [2]. The generated ROS subsequently attack almost all cell components including membrane lipids, producing lipid peroxidation [36].

The cytogenetic results of present study demonstrate that aluminum chloride induced a dose dependent significant increase in the frequencies of total chromosomal aberrations in bone marrow cells and spermatocytes of male rats.

Oxidative stress-induced damage was shown to be one of the important mechanisms to indicate that aluminum has an association with the chromosomal aberrations induction. Increased generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and lipid peroxidation has been found to be involved in the increase the chromosomal aberrations ratio. Aluminium is a non-redox active metal which is capable of increasing the cellular oxidative milieu by potentiating the pro-oxidant properties of transition metals such as iron and copper. It has been shown that chronic aluminium exposure is involved in the impairment of mitochondrial electron transport chain (ETC) and increased production of ROS. The formation of excessive ROS and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) can lead to oxidative injury. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) interact with all biological macromolecules, including lipids, proteins, nucleic acids (DNA and RNA), and carbohydrates.

Administration of *J. candicans* and *J. montana* extracts showed significant decrease in the frequencies of total chromosomal aberrations induced in bone marrow cells and spermatocytes of rats were treated with $AlCl_3$.

Also the current results revealed the non-toxic nature of *J. Candicans* and *J. montana* on normal rate, this result is greatly supported by other studies [37]. They reported that using oxidative stress analysis and gene expression profile in AD-induced rats *Jasonia montana* and *Jasonia candicans* were effective against Alzheimer's disease.

The above result suggests that both *J. montana* and *J. candicans* extracts may exert antioxidant activities high

content of flavonoids and phenolic compounds has been deconstructed in *J. montana* extract [38], as well as in *J. candicans* one [39], which may be responsible for antigenotoxicity and reduce the cytogenetic effect. The chromosomal aberrations assay provided evidence of genotoxicity of $AlCl_3$ and antigenotoxicity of *J. montana* and *J. candicans*.

In conclusion:

the results clearly suggested that the ethanolic extracts of aerial parts of *Jasonia candicans* or *Jasonia montana* may effectively ameliorate the oxidative stress induced by $AlCl_3$. Thus, these extracts may have therapeutic applications in the management of oxidative stress related diseases.

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